

**PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND MENTAL HEALTH: TEACHER'S CONTRIBUTIONS
TO THE WORK PROCESS IN PUBLIC HEALTH**

EDUCACIÓN FÍSICA Y SALUD MENTAL: CONTRIBUCIONES DE UN PROFESOR PARA EL
PROCESO DE TRABAJO EN SALUD COLECTIVA

EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA E SAÚDE MENTAL: CONTRIBUIÇÕES DE UM PROFESSOR PARA O
PROCESSO DE TRABALHO EM SAÚDE COLETIVA

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Abstract

This article aims to describe and analyze the work process in health based on the experiences of a Physical Education Teacher (PET) at a Psychosocial Care Center for Alcohol and Other Drugs III (CAPS AD III). It seeks to provide insights to support the continued implementation of the principles of Brazil's Psychiatric Reform (PR) within the fields of Mental Health (MH) and the Unified Health System (SUS). The article presents an assessment of positive vectors, obstacles, and setbacks, highlighting health work, underfunding, and the challenges posed by capitalist policies. It is a narrative of experiences as a mental health resident working at CAPS AD III in Aracaju/SE from March 2020 to March 2021. Concurrently, it engages with the realities of Public Health immersion, emphasizing ethical-political horizons, the financialization of healthcare. This approach enables identification of the limitations and possibilities for the role of the PET and other professionals in the field, as well as the challenges surrounding interactions with mental illness, substance abuse, the SUS, MH, and PR. It is concluded that the experience at CAPS AD III provided a reorientation of training in Mental Health, as well as contributed to expanding clinical practice in the construction of healthcare alongside other professionals and in the search for strategies that enable the participation of the Physical Education field. It highlights that the consolidation of the SUS remains incomplete; however, we believe in the possibility of reorganizing social health movements to develop strategies and envision possible paths to counter neoliberal policies.

Keywords: Mental Health; Public Health; Physical Education; Unified Health System; Work Process.

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Resumen

Con el objetivo de describir y analizar el proceso de trabajo en salud a través de las experiencias de un Profesor de Educación Física (PEF) en un Centro de Atención Psicosocial para Alcohol y otras Drogas III (CAPS AD III) en Aracaju/SE, entre marzo de 2020 y marzo de 2021, busca contribuir a la implementación de los principios de la Reforma Psiquiátrica (RP) en el campo de la Salud Mental (SM) y el Sistema Único de Salud (SUS) en Brasil. Se presenta un balance entre logros y obstáculos, abordando el subfinanciamiento del sistema de salud y los efectos adversos de políticas capitalistas. Desde una perspectiva de Salud Colectiva, el relato destaca horizontes ético-políticos y la financiarización de la salud, utilizando una perspectiva marxista del trabajo para examinar las limitaciones y potencialidades en la labor del PEF y otros trabajadores. El texto señala los desafíos en la relación con la locura, el consumo problemático de sustancias, el SUS y la RP. Se concluye que la experiencia en el CAPS AD III permitió la reorientación de la formación en SM, además de contribuir a ampliar la clínica en la construcción del cuidado en salud junto con otros profesionales y en la búsqueda de estrategias que posibiliten la actuación del núcleo de EF. Se señala que la consolidación del SUS está inconclusa; creemos en la posibilidad de reorganizar los movimientos sociales de la salud con el fin de construir estrategias y visualizar caminos posibles para enfrentar las políticas neoliberales.

Palabras clave: Salud Mental; Salud Colectiva; Educación Física; Sistema Único de Salud; Proceso de trabajo.

Resumo

Com o objetivo de descrever e analisar o processo de trabalho em saúde através das experiências vividas por um Professor de Educação Física (PEF) em um Centro de Atenção Psicossocial Álcool e outras Drogas III (CAPS AD III), o artigo visa ofertar subsídios para a continuação da implementação dos pressupostos da Reforma Psiquiátrica (RP) brasileira no campo da Saúde Mental (SM) e SUS. Apresenta um balanço de vetores positivos, obstáculos e retrocessos, sublinhando o trabalho em saúde, o subfinanciamento e os ataques pelas políticas do capital. Trata-se de um relato das experiências enquanto residente em SM ao atuar no CAPS AD III de Aracaju/SE, entre março de 2020 à março de 2021. Ao mesmo tempo dialoga com a realidade desde a imersão na Saúde Coletiva, ressaltando os horizontes ético-políticos e a financeirização da saúde. Torna-se possível identificar os limites e possibilidades quanto à atuação do PEF e demais trabalhadores no campo, assim como os desafios que perpassam as relações com a loucura e uso problemático de substâncias, o SUS, a SM e RP. Conclui-se que a vivência no CAPS AD III proporcionou a reorientação da formação em SM, assim como contribuiu ampliar a clínica na construção do cuidado em saúde com outros profissionais e na busca de estratégias que possibilitassem a atuação do núcleo da EF. Aponta que a consolidação do SUS está inconclusa, acreditamos na possibilidade da reorganização dos movimentos sociais da saúde a fim de construir estratégias e visualizar caminhos possíveis para enfrentar as políticas neoliberais.

Palavras-chave: Saúde Mental; Saúde Coletiva; Educação Física; Sistema Único de Saúde; Processo de trabalho.

Initial Considerations

From the inseparability between work and training, this article aims to contribute to the role of Physical Education (PE) teachers and other healthcare professionals in the field of public and collective health, specifically in the care of people who use alcohol and other drugs, concerning the work process at the Psychosocial Care Center for Alcohol and

Other Drugs III (CAPS AD III) in Aracaju/SE. This is based on experiences lived during the period of training and practice through the Multidisciplinary Residency in Mental Health at the Federal University of Sergipe (RMSM-UFS) from March 2020 to March 2021. While signaling historical advances in the Brazilian Sanitary Reform (RSB), the Brazilian Psychiatric Reform (RPB), and the Anti-asylum Struggle (LA), we will engage in dialogue with Physical Education (PE) and the context in which we are inserted, aiming to offer support to the field of Mental Health (SM) and the Unified Health System (SUS).

The Psychosocial Care Centers (CAPS) were established in 2002 through Ministerial Ordinance (PM) 336. They are specialized points of care aimed at treating individuals with moderate to severe mental disorders, including those related to alcohol and other drug use, and integrate the Psychosocial Care Network (RAPS) (Brazil, 2011). These services are the result of the struggles of the Brazilian Sanitary Reform Movement, the Psychiatric Reform, and the Anti-asylum Struggle, which focused on reorganizing mental health care in Brazil for individuals with psychological suffering, in alignment with the principles and guidelines of SUS (Amarante, 2007). This has made it possible for physical education teachers to join the multidisciplinary team.

The aspirations for democracy, the crisis in social security, and the economic recession of the 1970s in Brazil contributed to the emergence of the Sanitary Reform Movement, advocating for health as a social and political issue, rather than solely a biological one to be addressed by medical services (Paim et al., 2011). Simultaneously, Brazilian society and the Mental Health Workers Movement began mobilizing against "genocidal isolation and the commodification of madness" (Vasconcelos, 2000, p. 23). From this, Costa and Faria (2021) highlight that this process was crucial for the Psychiatric Reform movement and a series of struggles that culminated in achievements such as the 1988 Federal Constitution (CF 88) and the SUS – Unified Health System (Costa; Faria, 2021).

The Brazilian Psychiatric Reform (RPB) was influenced by the ideas of Italian Franco Basaglia, based on deinstitutionalization, envisioning health care focused on the production of life, collective spaces formed by solidarity and affectivity. These ideas were incorporated and encouraged by the Brazilian Sanitary Reform (RSB). The Mental Health Workers Movement was vital to this process and peaked with the formation of the National Anti-asylum Struggle Network, increasing dialogue with society (Queiroz, 2012).

In this context, Queiroz (2012) emphasizes the 1989 Bill of then-deputy Paulo Delgado, the regulation of SUS, and the guarantee of social participation through Laws No. 8.080 and 8.142 of 1990, the Caracas Declaration in 1990, and the establishment of the National Commission for Mental Health in 1991 to formulate and implement policies in the area.

Among the main Ministerial Ordinances (PM) are No. 224 of 1992 and PM No. 106 of 2000. The first legitimizes the creation of Psychosocial Care Centers (CAPS) and Psychosocial Care Nuclei (NAPS) based on the principles and guidelines of SUS, while the second creates and regulates Therapeutic Residential Services (SRT). In 2001, after twelve years, Law 10.2016, or the Paulo Delgado Law, was enacted, which promotes changes in the mental health care model and boosts the National Mental Health Policy (Queiroz, 2012).

Therefore, we face at least two important points related to the work process within SUS: the need for continuing education through Permanent Health Education (EPS) policies for workers, as well as the need for strategies to reorient training in health courses, through curriculum reforms, projects, and research that bring students closer to the reality of SUS in order to implement its principles and guidelines, and strengthen the Psychiatric Reform and Anti-asylum Struggle that are still under construction. Among the strategies to reorient health training in undergraduate and graduate programs, we can highlight projects like PET-Saúde⁵, VER-SUS Brazil, and Multidisciplinary Health Residencies⁶.

However, the hegemonic training in health follows a curriculum structure centered on the transmission of hierarchical and vertical knowledge (Fraga; Carvalho; Gomes, 2012; Carvalho, 2016), perpetuated by conservative models and institutions that approach the health-disease process “[...] through single-causal explanations, biologism, fragmentation, mechanistic views, nosocentrism, recovery and rehabilitation, technicalism, and specialization” (Cutolo, 2006, p. 16). Thus, there is a training based on the hospital-centered logic and the medicalization of life, focusing on the resolutiveness of health

⁵ The Education through Work in Health Program (PET-Health) was launched in 2007 as a partnership between the Ministry of Health (MS) and the Ministry of Education (MEC). Its purpose is to promote the reorientation of health education, including Physical Education. The program is grounded in the teaching-service-community approach, using active methodologies to strengthen both multidisciplinary and interdisciplinarity

⁶ Between 2003 and 2004, the Project for Experiences and Internships in the Reality of the Unified Health System – VER-SUS/Brazil – was launched, challenging traditional notions of teaching and learning. In 2004, the *Aprender-SUS* initiative and the National Policy on Permanent Education in the SUS (Unified Health System) were also introduced.

problems and needs in attention models that invest resources in high technology and high-complexity hospitals. The impact of this can also be observed in the relationships established between Physical Education (PE) and Mental Health (MH), or between physical activity and MH in Brazil and internationally (Furtado et al., 2022).

Historically, the relationship between PE and the health field has ties with the development of physical fitness influenced by hygienism, eugenics, and militarism. Starting in the 19th century, the naturalized concept became fundamental to justify an increasingly contradictory society, as it had never seen so much wealth (accumulated by a minority) and so much misery produced, explaining social factors under a biological lens. Basic concepts about the body were elaborated in order to invest in a new man, develop physical aptitudes, and discipline him. A body unconcerned with its history, focused on physiology and anatomy, explained through positivist science (Soares, 2006).

Supported by the biomedical discourse, PE limited its meanings and significances by conditioning a view that often tended to disregard the subjectivity of individuals within a given social, political, and economic context, evidenced by different ways of living, access to transport, leisure, housing, sanitation, food, etc., that is, what came to be understood through the (critical) perspective of the social determinants of health (DSS), aligned with an intersectional perspective of totality and social markers such as race/ethnicity, gender, sexualities, and social classes in the determination of the health-disease process (Oliveira, 2018).

Pasquim et al. (2023) affirm that the inclusion of PE teachers in SUS was encouraged starting in 2002 with the possibility of composing multidisciplinary teams at the CAPS and in the Family Health Support Nuclei (NASF) in 2008, strengthening with the implementation of the Health Academy Program (PAS).

In the field of PE, knowledge can be built from either traditional or social epidemiology. In the former, meanings and interpretations are conditioned to a natural and scientific view of movement and health indicators based on biomedical rationality, linked to improving physical fitness, with interventions prioritizing reducing the impact of chronic diseases, grounded in biology and physiology. International literature defines studies between PE, physical activity, and mental health based on specific diagnoses,

symptoms, and biochemical responses, emphasizing the effects of physical activity on health parameters. A shortage of interventions that go beyond the development of physical conditioning and motor skills can be identified (Oliveira, 2018; Furtado et al., 2022; Wachs, 2016; Roble et al., 2012).

In relation to social epidemiology, it is understood that social and biological life conditions are interrelated and complement each other, with neither being prioritized at the expense of the other. From a dialectical perspective in health, the aim is to overcome the biomedical paradigm in an attempt to build integrality through body⁷, mediated by Body Culture⁸, emphasizing the development of human consciousness as "[...] historical, political, and social subjects who have the capacity to intervene in reality" (Oliveira, 2018, p. 14). It becomes necessary to develop evaluation tools based on social, economic, physiological, and biological conditions (Oliveira, 2018).

Like any new journey, the experience report aims to present the possibilities that a new practice can bring to existing processes. The presence of PE teachers in health is not necessarily new. It has increasingly become a reality in SUS. However, the introduction of health care technologies/tools related to the work process takes some time to produce changes, just as formative practices in various curricula do. Thus, the experience report functions to describe, share, analyze, and discuss the work process in mental health through lived experiences, the incorporation of care practices and tools, and the establishment of a dialogical relationship in the work-formation connection.

As Ceccim (2005) points out, we need to value the workspace as a territory where practices are more than just achievements of experience, emerging as teaching-learning processes and analyses of self-production and the production of worlds. In this direction, the workplace is not only a space for application but also a space for resistance and

⁷ In the context of documents guiding public health policies, the term Body Practices/Physical Activity (PCAF) appears in the 2006 National Health Promotion Policy (PNPS). It highlights the practical possibilities for the involvement of Physical Education professionals in Primary Health Care (PHC) and in the community. The concept goes beyond widely disseminated technical exercises, encompassing broader meanings rooted in the contents of Body Culture. (Wagner, 2007).

⁸ In turn, Body Culture is expressed through representations of the world and bodily language that human beings have developed throughout history, made visible through body expressions and practices such as games, dances, circus and adventure activities, martial arts, sports, and gymnastics. It has the potential to break with the biologicist paradigm by recognizing the "symbolic representation of realities experienced by human beings, historically created and culturally developed" (Soares et al., 1991, p. 26).

creation. In this context, territory is not confined to a physical or geographic space; it is a "[...] space of meaning inscription in work, through work, and by work" (Ceccim, 2005, p. 983).

For it to be educational, this territory needs to be inhabited by learning processes that value its singularities, ensuring attention to the movements occurring there and allowing for sensitive exploration, as well as the construction of autonomy. Therefore, it seems necessary to design work processes capable of seeking invention in the daily practices. Specifically, we focus on the mode of work in health, which aims to develop care practices.

Thus, from this contextualization that briefly presented the panorama of Brazilian public/collective health and the specific scenario of PE, the experience report continues in the next section, presenting the methodological aspects of the experience and then the results and discussions, and finally sharing reflections and insights from the experience.

Methodological Notes on the Experience

As previously mentioned, the aim of this report is to share and analyze the work process carried out at the Centro de Atenção Psicossocial Álcool e outras Drogas III (CAPS AD III) in Aracaju, Sergipe, based on the concrete reality experienced as a Physical Education Teacher (PEF) due to participation in the Multidisciplinary Residency Program in Mental Health at the Federal University of Sergipe (UFS), from March 2020 to March 2021.

Initially, we describe the activities carried out in the service alongside the multiprofessional team, followed by an analysis of the multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary praxis, highlighting the contradictions present in the work process within this societal project. In the third phase, we bring the role of Physical Education into the debate.

Regarding the nature of the work, this is a descriptive study, and with regard to data approach, it is qualitative, as it allowed for the analysis of various perceptions, as well as the relationships, views, and judgments of different social agents involved with situations in the Multidisciplinary Residency in Mental Health, as well as the context of actions and services. This assumes that experiences and reactions are part of the intervention

construction and its results. In relation to its objectives, it is characterized as a report of experience, i.e., a description of lived experiences by one or more agents, aimed at fostering discussions and contributing to reality based on lived experience (Silva et al., 2021; Santos, 2021; Minayo, 2004; Oliveira et al., 2017).

This article is an excerpt from the Residency Conclusion Work (TCR) with the same title, presented to UFS, São Cristóvão campus, in 2022, as a requirement for obtaining the title of specialist in mental health. The Centro de Atenção Psicossocial Álcool e outras Drogas III (CAPS AD III) is located in the southern area of Aracaju, Sergipe, and was implemented in 2002 as CAPS AD, providing care to people with abusive alcohol and drug use starting at 28 years old; those below this age are served in another service. In 2011, under Ministerial Ordinance (PM) 3.088, it was requalified to CAPS AD III.

CAPS AD III units were established in 2010 and redefined in 2012, in a context of expanding care strategies for individuals with needs related to alcohol, crack, and other drug use. These facilities are 24-hour attention points, operating every day of the week, distinguishing them from CAPS AD. They have multiprofessional teams and physical structures that enable the provision of overnight accommodation (Brasil, 2012).

Aracaju, located in the Northeast Region, is the capital and the primary political and economic center of the state of Sergipe. According to the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), the estimated population in 2020 was 664,908 (IBGE, 2020), although the 2022 census accounted for 602,757 people (IBGE, 2022). In the 2019 Social Mapping 2019, based on the 2010 census, there was a concentration of households in poverty in the peripheral areas of the city, located at the northern and southern extremes, in regions that have been experiencing disorganized occupation in recent years (Aracaju, 2019).

The map of the spatial concentration of the Black/Brown population shows that 66% of the population self-identified as part of these groups and is concentrated in the peripheral territories of the city, while 32% identified as White, concentrating in the city's central region, where the per capita household income is higher. The authors point out a correlation between average income and the ethnic/racial profile of the population. Additionally, 1% self-identified as Indigenous, and 1% as Yellow (Aracaju, 2019). In this sense, the location of CAPS AD III in the southern area is contradictory, as most service users are Black or Brown, many of whom live in peripheral areas, and some are homeless. During the experience, many individuals mentioned the difficulty of reaching the service, which could be considered a barrier to access.

During the period of this experience (between 2020 and 2021), the original building, located on the same street, was undergoing renovations and was operating in a house rented by the municipality from 2013 to 2022. The insertion of this professional in the described context is marked by the historical period characterized by the implications and impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The Multidisciplinary Residency Program in Mental Health at UFS was implemented in 2010 and includes residents from pharmacy, nursing, social work, and psychology. It was only in 2015 that Physical Education (PE) was included, and recently, occupational therapy was added. It is worth noting that the present report occurs within a training context, in a residency program, which will be described in the first person, from the account of cases and situations experienced by the resident (the first author of this text) and analyzed collectively by the authors of this article in the nucleus tutor spaces (residents and tutors). Therefore, collective analysis of situations and systematic analyses of the work process were produced. Thus, the writing will be composed in both the first-person singular and plural forms.

The Work Process at CAPS AD III

Since 2007, the Ministry of Health (MS) has highlighted the Psychosocial Care Network (RAPS/REAPS) in Aracaju (SE) as one of the best municipal networks dedicated to treating people with mental disorders and those who use alcohol and other drugs. The Cactus Institute (2021), when disclosing the evaluation of mental health indicators in Brazil, indicates that the municipality ranks fourth in the number of CAPS per 100,000 inhabitants, behind Presidente Prudente (RJ), Campina Grande (PB), and Campinas (SP). Additionally, the Damage Reduction Program (PRD) is currently funded by the municipality itself.

The concept of mental health is directly linked to social issues, leading us to examine our society to explain the increase in social inequalities and contradictions from the 19th century onwards. Therefore, thinking about mental health is also about understanding social issues, such as inequality, wealth distribution, structural unemployment, and others (Costa; Faria, 2021; Amarante, 2007).

In this context, in an article titled "A Spell Without Farofa and Without a Candle: Food Insecurity as an Analyzer of Psychosocial Care," developed during the Covid-19 pandemic, within the same Mental Health Network (REAPS) in Aracaju/SE, Coutinho, Vasconcelos, and Amorim (2023, p.553) present the following questions: "[...] can collective mental health be produced without looking into the eyes of hunger? What enchantments in psychosocial care can mislead the hunger for food and the expansion of life?".

The authors, analyzing the management data of RAPS during the Covid-19 pandemic, point to the need to consider the various forms of hunger because "[...] the task of listening to hunger for food, affection, music demands inventions of satiation" that mobilize the work processes in mental health to "[...] produce a psychosocial care that misleads hunger in RAPS requires the task of deinstitutionalizing cities" (Coutinho; Vasconcelos; Amorim, 2023, p. 553).

The work process in mental health is not limited to tracking the effects of a specific pathology or the biological effects of substance use and abuse. In a CAPS, the work process should be based on care in freedom and the logic of damage reduction, meaning it considers the variations in usage and users, as it is the relationship between people and the substance that determines whether the use is problematic. The perception of care should surpass the stigmatization that classifies users as mad, marginal, or "rotten" (Santos; Miranda, 2016).

In a CAPS, the work process is grounded in the theoretical-methodological framework of matrix support, based on the multiprofessional integration of different fields (Brazil, 2013). The work process is developed from the perspective of care in freedom. In 2020, the multiprofessional team at CAPS AD III was without a doctor but included a social worker, psychologist, pharmacist, occupational therapist, physical education teacher, nurse, nursing technicians and assistants, two pharmacy residents, one social service resident, and one physical education resident. There were also general service professionals, security guards, administrative technicians, and a manager.

The multiprofessional team was divided into two mini-teams, one serving the population from the northern area and the other from the southern area. Each professional in the team was a Reference Technician (TR) for a group of users, taking responsibility for them, although health care was shared. The service provided therapeutic workshops, user assemblies, mini-team meetings, active searches, home visits, individual and shared care.

The construction of the Singular Therapeutic Project (PTS)⁹ aims to organize and guide the care process for users, being created within the mini-team, agreed upon with the user, and presented in technical meetings. The PTS establishes the frequency of service attendance, therapeutic workshops, and user participation in activities.

Regarding the CAPS infrastructure, at the beginning of the residency: the house was very old, with dirty walls, broken windows, few rooms for consultations, and many walls with mold. The official renovation had been delayed for eight years, and at that time, it had still not been completed¹⁰.

In the second week of March 2020, the entire work process was remodeled with the advent of the Covid-19 pandemic and the municipality's Contingency Plan. After a meeting, a drastic reduction in the number of users was implemented, and social isolation was adopted. A hygiene flow was established for everyone entering the premises, a rotation system for professionals (working one shift per week), and compensatory hours were to be done remotely, as well as all meetings taking place remotely. Group activities were suspended, and individual care or reception was conducted outdoors, using masks and maintaining social distancing.

Discussions were intensified, as it was necessary to classify the risk in reception, guiding social isolation, and it was possible to focus more on the severe cases attended by the service, given the reduced number of users. For Gondim (2020), the pandemic scenario recalls Foucault's studies on biopolitics, territories, and security, the first being related to the power that governs life policies, i.e., strategies, technologies, practices, and rationalities that decide which bodies should live and which should be discarded.

⁹ The Singular Therapeutic Project (PTS) is a set of coordinated therapeutic approaches designed for the user or their family. It results from discussions within an interdisciplinary team and serves as a tool for organizing health care. This plan is built collaboratively between the team and the user, taking into account the unique characteristics and complexity of each case. By identifying health needs, discussing diagnoses, and defining shared care strategies, the PTS can enhance treatment effectiveness, as improved communication strengthens bonds and increases the level of shared responsibility da comunicação traz o fortalecimento dos vínculos e o aumento do grau de corresponsabilização (Brasil, 2014).

¹⁰ Currently, the CAPS AD III is housed in a new structure following the renovation of the former CAPS, which previously functioned as a meat market. Vasconcelos and Seffener (2017), in the article “*For a Political-Ethics of Narrativity in the Meat Market*”, describe bodies marked by neglect—users of alcohol and other drugs who would spend hours sprawled across the marble tables of the old market—resembling the dead meat that once occupied the same space.

Dantas et al. (2020) highlight that the National Health Council (CNS) advised that the theoretical-practical activities of residents should follow the reorganization of services, networks, policies, and actions in the health sector's rapid response to COVID-19. However, only residents were forced to return to services under the threat of scholarship cuts and were reassigned to any health service, even if their residency was focused on mental health. As a result, some residents were sent to airports to participate in triage for incoming flights, and others were to be reassigned to field hospitals being built. But this did not occur due to the mobilization of the residents' collective, highlighting the emphasis on high complexity over primary care and mental health (medium complexity/specialized), as well as the devaluation and lack of labor rights for residents.

At CAPS AD III, 10 residents were supposed to compose the practical scenario, but only 3 remained (a physical education resident and two pharmacists) after mobilizations, as some residents were reassigned to other services in the Psychosocial Care Network (RAPS), and others entered remote work due to greater risk of exposure.

Strategies/Tools for Mental Health Care

Mental health care practices “must promote new possibilities for transforming and enhancing life conditions and ways of living, guided by the production of life and health” (Brazil, 2013, p. 23). The services provided began to include welcoming practices, network coordination, individual and shared appointments, team meetings, continuing health education, and nighttime reception. These activities form the work processes developed by the team in an effort to provide mental health care. They may be referred to as actions, technologies, strategies, or tools of care, expressed in various ways by different professionals.

Welcoming must occur continuously throughout the user's care journey; it is a strategy designed to enhance the quality of care and enable fairer, broader, and more comprehensive access (Coutinho; Vasconcelos; Amorim, 2023). For new users, an initial welcoming session was carried out through qualified listening, making it possible to assess whether the case fit the profile for specialized (moderate to severe) care, or whether the

demand should be safely referred to primary care or social services, as many sought shelter or other forms of social support. When the demand was related to psychoactive substance use, the case was discussed by the multidisciplinary team, and the Individual Therapeutic Project (Projeto Terapêutico Singular – PTS) was developed together with the user. Initially, these sessions were accompanied by the preceptor; over time, they were conducted individually as needed.

Individual appointments were held at least once a day, with emphasis on specific individual sessions, shared appointments, or interconsultations. Individual sessions usually occurred when the Reference Technician (Técnico de Referência – TR) was unavailable, or when a strong bond had been established with the user. Depending on the complexity of the case, it was brought to either the full team or a smaller subgroup for discussion.

Shared appointments and interconsultations are mental health care tools that originated during the Psychiatric Reform movement in the 1980s, which included the establishment of psychiatric units in general hospitals. These are considered “light technologies” that enhance care comprehensiveness, qualify service delivery, and facilitate the exchange of knowledge among professionals. They involve joint consultations with professionals from different backgrounds. These were conducted at least once daily and allowed for shared care, more robust case discussions, and more effective therapeutic planning, while promoting interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary collaboration.

The “logbook” was an important communication tool—a notebook where individual and shared referrals were recorded—helping to prevent fragmentation in care and work processes. By the time professionals attended team meetings, they were already aware of what had taken place, such as incidents, group activities, new user intakes, and so on.

Weekly team meetings were held on Thursdays in a remote format with the entire CAPS team. These meetings were opportunities to discuss work processes and reflect on practices and service operations. Discussions covered territory-specific issues, user needs, and professional challenges. Based on experience, case discussions proved to be highly impactful, contributing to both interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary work.

In this sense, effective interdisciplinarity offers pathways to pluralistic care in which the user becomes the central point of convergence for various disciplines and support practices. This approach advances toward comprehensive care, moving away from reductionist models that disregard subjectivity and social variables (Brazil, 2015). Mendes et al. (2021) confirm that team meetings are strategies that help restructure care delivery by facilitating decision-making among professionals with different backgrounds.

Matrix support meetings were reduced during the pandemic as many services shifted to remote operations. However, some meetings continued with CAPS teams who shared users, including those from Basic Health Units (UBS), the Harm Reduction Project (PRD), Street Clinic (CnR), and Social Assistance Reference Centers (CRAS).

Together with the UBS, the project “CAPOSSIBILIDADES: Territory of Affection” was developed. Conceived by the preceptor, it involved mapping the social infrastructure in the Santa Maria neighborhood (on the outskirts of Aracaju) with the help of Community Health Agents (ACS) and harm reduction agents. The aim was to identify protective factors that could support mental health care for CAPS AD III users living in the area. A document was produced containing addresses, phone numbers, contact persons, available services, and other relevant information to strengthen ties between users and local resources.

Continuing Health Education (Educação Permanente em Saúde – EPS) was questioned by residents, as knowledge about mental health and work processes was not always aligned. Manicomial (asylum-based) practices were still common in the service. Some professionals advocated for abstinence, restriction of liberty, and compulsory admission to Therapeutic Communities as the main care strategy—positions that reinforce stigma and contradict the principles of the Psychosocial Care Network (RAPS) in Brazil’s Unified Health System (SUS). Mendes et al. (2021) highlight the importance of EPS in care management, as it enables interpersonal, organizational, and work process transformations.

Residents implemented the “Tree of Life” strategy, where a single tree was drawn, and professionals wrote down words related to their work processes and what they wished to change, symbolizing the production of new “fruits.” From this, themes such as care in freedom, mental health care fragmentation, and harm reduction were identified for discussion. Some workers volunteered to organize and lead future EPS sessions.

Theoretical discussions were based on studies in Public Health and Mental Health, and on day-to-day practice at CAPS. These included academic texts, documentaries, and guest lectures from professionals formerly involved with the RAPS in Aracaju-SE. Pausing care activities to promote EPS proved meaningful, as it reflected in changes to care practices and helped challenge the view that deprivation of liberty is an appropriate treatment for users of alcohol and other drugs. Team conflicts also diminished during meetings, allowing for greater alignment in constructing the PTS.

Network coordination is also essential to building comprehensive mental health care and facilitates knowledge exchange among professionals. The therapeutic project integrated health-related matters (follow-up or referral to other health services) with social concerns such as document recovery, shelter requests, financial management, creation and management of emails, and use of online services. The focus of this strategy is not to control the user, but to provide conditions for them to access services and sustain care longitudinally. For example, during the pandemic, professionals helped users apply for emergency financial aid (a temporary income support policy), which required setting up email accounts, consulting social workers, accompanying users to withdraw money, and organizing finances.

Home visits were conducted both in residences and on the streets, recognizing the street as a place of dwelling. Active outreach was also performed when users failed to attend scheduled sessions. If a user staying in the nighttime reception facility tested positive for COVID-19 or was suspected of infection, they were referred to an emergency isolation shelter. For those with housing, home isolation was recommended for a certain period.

One available option was referral to the Adult Reception Unit (Unidade de Acolhimento Adulto – UAA). When a user developed new life prospects but lacked the means to maintain them, the UAA served as a residential facility where they could stay for up to six months, with the goal of rebuilding social ties. CAPS played a mediating role in this process, which was jointly developed with the multidisciplinary teams of CAPS, the UAA, and the user, following the therapeutic project and subject to ongoing evaluation.

Throughout the pandemic, the “Good Morning” meeting was held every morning—a gathering of users and professionals. This space was used to share information about service offerings, self-care guidance related to the pandemic, the need for social

distancing, popular education topics, and the importance of social oversight. Users also used the time to voice concerns, such as the need for supplies, longer stays at the service, and a greater variety of activities.

The “good days” happened throughout the pandemic: a morning meeting between users and professionals. In this space, information was transmitted about service offers, self-care guidelines in relation to the pandemic, the need for social isolation, popular education topics, the importance of social control, among other questions. Users also agreed to express their concerns, such as the need for materials, the demand for more time in the service and the supply of more activities in the place.

In the second half of 2020, following new municipal guidelines and the easing of isolation measures, the number of users increased, and professionals resumed in-person activities, with the exception of meetings, which remained remote. Group activities were also gradually restructured.

Group activities became part of the service offerings, including recreational workshops like karaoke, bingo, and festive events for São João, Christmas, and Carnival, all within the constraints of COVID-19 prevention protocols. Films and documentaries such as *Bacurau*, *City of God*, and *City of God: 10 Years Later* were screened to create meaning, spark discussion, and prompt participants to reflect on their lived realities.

As team development and work processes evolve through the articulation and agreements of multiprofessional teams, they also occur dialectically within a uniprofessional perspective. This is due to the differing educational backgrounds, life experiences, and professional guidelines among team members, which directly impact the application—or the lack of—mental health care tools.

Specificities of Physical Education in Mental Health

In the daily operations of the SUS, the predominant model is medical-centered, biologically based, hospital-centric, and medicalized. Biomedical content is frequently used to legitimize the role of Physical Education Professionals (PEPs) in the fields of Mental and Collective Health. Scientific studies show that physical exercises and activities can provoke

physiological and biochemical reactions in the body, and many professionals use this discourse to justify their practices.

In Primary Health Care (PHC) or Mental Health (MH), it is common for workers to pressure the performance of stretches at the beginning of activities, without a clear objective, merely to fill the PEP's schedule, who is there to promote relaxation, movement, or occupy the users' time in the service. Thus, we have a social representation of what is expected from the PEP in the Multiprofessional Residency in Mental Health, based on the traditional view of Physical Education, i.e., a reductionist perspective understood merely as physical exercise.

Often, these representations are reinforced by the media, which portrays this professional's role as limited to activities with which they themselves may not feel comfortable, such as workshops, groups, outings, and event organization. On the other hand, users often demand football as the only option for physical activity, as it has historically been presented to them as the sole alternative – a situation also observed in the school context, where Physical Education classes are seen as time and space for playing football.

The audience at the CAPS AD III (Psychosocial Care Center for Alcohol and Drugs) was predominantly male, immersed in a football culture promoted by the media, high-performance sports, the sportification of school Physical Education, and the pervasive machismo present across all races/ethnicities and classes in the Brazilian context. Football, being the most practiced sport in the country, is dominated by one gender. Although it should not be excluded as an element that constitutes sports and physical activities, football needs to be understood as a social practice that humanizes, contributing to human development, therapeutic project construction, and healthcare.

However, football should not be the only option. It is necessary to develop strategies to explore other sports and physical practices, to which most users have no access. For instance, combat sports, ancient practices, can be used to discuss the differences between fights and brawls, and to engage with combat games while inviting external professionals to share experiences in a specific modality. Dance, as a physical practice directly related to art, can also be used to deconstruct gender, sexuality, race/ethnicity, and religion-related stigmas, fostering socialization, body awareness, cultural appropriation, and autonomy.

When observing that users played dominoes individually and with betting, it was decided to organize a championship. Games stimulate the meaning of actions, develop skills, and make participants more aware of their choices and decisions. Unlike the usual way of playing, the championship was held in pairs, with eliminations and a "second chance" round, allowing losing teams to recover the following day. In addition to the commitment to attend the next day, discussions were held on trust, competitiveness, support between game partners, as well as issues related to discrimination, such as labeling someone as "strong" or "weak," and the importance of sharing feelings and thoughts. Conflicts were resolved through dialogue, opening space to address the topic of violence. Popular games were also used at other times to strengthen bonds and as leisure activities.

Walks to a public park in the southern part of the city became part of the weekly routine, providing moments of relaxation. Upon arrival, stretching exercises were performed with explanations on their importance, indicating which body parts were being stretched, the names of the muscles involved, how these muscles are used in daily activities, and the need for self-awareness and self-care, considering each individual's subjectivity. Based on the set objectives, stretches are not merely an alternative in the absence of other activities, but a strategy for self-care, health education, and body awareness, as well as aiding flexibility and the understanding of one's own and others' body limits and possibilities.

During the walks, doubts and suggestions arose, and other professionals engaged in the process, sometimes leading a music circle. At the end, an assessment of the space was conducted to identify participants' perceptions, meaning-making, and to improve future activities. The proposed activities were discussed beforehand in meetings and followed protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19.

However, to claim that physical activities or exercises alone contribute to health conditions excludes the subjectivities related to the production of health in human beings. For instance, during the park walks, some users opted to ride in the service vehicle as they had already walked throughout the city the previous night. Nonetheless, this activity may have contributed positively to the users' therapeutic projects.

Physical Education teachers, in the process of working in mental health, can follow guidelines and use care tools outlined in documents such as the *Cadernos da Atenção Básica* (n. 34, 2012) and the *Cadernos da Política Nacional de Humanização* (v. 5, 2015), both dedicated to mental health and prepared by the Ministry of Health (MS). These documents offer specific guidelines for multiprofessional teams. Generally, the weekly agenda may include individual appointments, shared consultations, mini-team meetings, collective activities, matrix support, and network articulation.

The development of body practices can be worked on transversally with the activities, discussed with users, and shared with the team, based on specific objectives and process evaluations. Beyond body practices, the provision of care in mental health requires an expanded and shared clinic¹¹, free from prejudice and stigmatization, addressing the resolution of social issues that generate health inequities.

Possibilities of Physical Education in mental health

The pandemic limited interventions that used collective physical practices in services, imposing the use of masks, social isolation, restrictions on touching others' bodies, and crowding. However, the work process at CAPS AD III contributed significantly to the training of Physical Education Professionals (PEPs) working in Public and Collective Health. The residency experience, and in the specific space, is treated as the professional and social place that allowed for the exploration of the possibilities and challenges in Mental Health concerning Physical Education actions.

The strength of team discussions, the deconstruction of historically built stereotypes, the praxis of Physical Education in mental health, and alignment with the Anti-

¹¹ The expanded clinic is a theoretical and practical tool whose objective is to contribute to a clinical approach to the nursing and suffering process, which considers the singularity of the subject and the complexity of the health/sickness process. It allows us to face the fragmentation of knowledge and actions in health, as well as their respective damage and inefficiency. It uses resources that enable the enrichment of diagnoses (other variables, in addition to the organic focus, including the perception of affects produced in clinical relationships) and the qualification of dialogue (both between health professionals involved in the treatment and between them and the user), in a way that shared decisions are made possible and committed to the autonomy and health of SUS users (Brasil, 2013, p.9).

Manicomial Fight were fundamental, especially because many workers in this service were active in the Psychiatric Reform process before the creation of CAPS in the city.

According to Costa and Faria (2021), Psychiatric Reform, as a complex social process, produced changes and achieved gains in the theoretical-assistive, legal-political, and sociocultural dimensions, enabling advances in care from an anti-asylum perspective materialized in substitute devices and networks. Although it did not aim at the renewal of psychiatry, this reform changed the way madness is understood and approached.

However, these advances have been questioned, and SUS itself has been weakened by neoliberal policies. Health practices in the daily care reflect the public policies advocated by the Health Reform movement. During the experience, it was possible to observe the deterioration of mental health, especially in the care line for Alcohol and Other Drugs (AD), as well as the fragmentation in relation to the care line for Mental Disorders and the dialogue with Primary Health Care (APS). As an example of the advancement of neoliberal policies, Costa and Faria (2021) highlight the rise of therapeutic communities, which raise questions about care in freedom, harm reduction, and the very existence of the CAPS service. In order for users' citizenship to be realized, it is necessary to transform and overcome this sociability, as it restricts humanity (Costa; Faria, 2021).

At times, the Municipal Guard would attend the service when intervention was needed. However, from 2021 onwards, it began to frequent the space daily. This presence exposes the criminalization of drugs, which is framed as a racist policy of incarceration and genocide of the Black population, part of a perspective of body doctrine, which denies the individual the autonomy to decide on the use of substances, camouflaged by moral and religious discourses.

Situations like these expose the war on drugs, evidencing necropolitics, which Mbembe (2018) defines when the State decides which bodies should live and which should die in an offensive and repressive system. However, it hides a highly profitable illicit market that drives the global economy, where a segment of the white population with high purchasing power has access without facing imminent risks. Ferrugem and Gershenson (2020) corroborate that "the global market for drug consumption only grows, as does the profit generated by illegal trade" (p. 206), adding that prohibitionism is "based from the

outset on racism, xenophobia, puritanism, and financial interests" (Ferrugem; Gershenson, 2020, p. 206).

The consumption of these substances increased during the pandemic due to isolation, increased unemployment, reduced income, food insecurity, and rising prices of basic consumption goods. **Oliveira, Santos and Dallaqua (2021, p.1)** point to the association between the pandemic period and the increase in people with mental disorders, as well as the "increase in the sale of medications like antidepressants, anxiolytics, and substances such as alcohol and illicit drugs".

During the experience, it was possible to observe that healthcare is still centered on the figure of the doctor and the prescription of medications. Medicalization proposes replacing illicit drugs with legal, prescribed ones, which, in some situations, can lead to another form of dependence. The very inclusion of physical education is justified as a potential enhancer of mental health by itself, as a natural medication, since many users lived with food insecurity, housing instability, and lack of access to basic consumer goods.

Moreover, many professionals complained about the high demand, devaluation of the profession, lack of public competitions, and the fragility of work ties, which are established through selective processes, as well as the outsourcing of the health sector, with the last public competition held in 2011.

PEFs are undervalued in SUS and, in CAPS, they work with the same workload, receiving the lowest salaries. Additionally, to record progress in the medical chart, they need the password of another professional, as their access is different from others. They are registered as "health caregivers," which does not allow full access to information. With the creation of the CBO in 2020, they gained access to the medical chart.

More broadly, the precariousness of PEF work extends to other areas of activity, especially in the private sector, linked to the impositions of restrictions from national and regional councils, the absence of a salary floor or employment ties, based on a system of payment per class/hour, fragmentation in undergraduate programs, disarticulation of social movements, and workers' lack of unity, most of whom fill their work hours across various institutions. This makes the articulation of students and workers within the field crucial to ensure professional rights.

The multiprofessional team often requests PEF participation to "fill gaps" in the service, reducing their actions to stretching practices or workshops, given their skills in working with groups. This points to the need to reflect on the meanings of Physical Education in multiprofessional mental health teams. We must continue seeking answers to the question raised by Machado (2011): "What is the institutional request made to Physical Education when entering the work processes in mental health?" Reflecting on the presence of Physical Education in the CAPS AD III multiprofessional team, we see that it broadens the possibilities for care, as practices involving Physical Education seem to, in our view, foster care practices that promote mental health care in an expanded perspective.

Thus, from a field perspective, experiences contributed to knowledge production through exchanges with other health professionals, intervening in health care without restricting to physical practices, as from the specific training in Physical Education, we can broaden our outlook on health. For example, recognizing that by helping a user resume their life project and daily activities, we are also contributing to improving their health conditions, as well as registering a user who cannot even recall their birth date, assisting in the street, creating an email, scheduling an appointment, or other forms of care that do not fit within the confines of a purely biomedical or institutional framework.

From the perspective of the specific Physical Education field, it was possible to seek strategies for physical practices to take place, recognizing that the prescribed "recipe" for one user is not a fixed formula that should be prescribed for others, as in the case of the walks where some users were too tired to walk and preferred to accompany the service vehicle, but still chose to go. Are we contributing to this person's mental health simply because they were seated?

The experiences in CAPS AD III not only reoriented health training but also personal growth, as the stereotypes (prejudice, marginalization, etc.) built up to that point were deconstructed in the daily operations of the service, in the care, in the bond, in visits, workshops, meetings, welcoming, and other activities. In this sense, it provided human, intellectual, political, and professional training through the transformations that occurred in the work process.

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